

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CERTAIN LABORATORY AND FUNCTIONAL INDICATORS IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES AND WITHOUT CHRONIC HEART FAILURE.

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Resume. In this scientific article, the functional state of the heart was assessed using echocardiography in patients with chronic heart failure with diabetes and without it [1,4,8,10]. Also, the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-6, TGF- β 1, potassium, urinary albuminuria and cystatin-C in the blood serum of patients and the speed of glomerular filtration using it were compared [2,3,6,9]. In patients with chronic heart failure and diabetes, it was found that the quality of life, the level of resistance to physical loads, and the clinical condition were reliably reduced compared to patients without diabetes [5,7].

Keywords: Chronic heart failure, interleukin-6, cystatin-S, glomerular filtration rate, β -transforming growth factor.

Actuality. In recent years, it has been noted that high comorbidity reduces quality of life, impairs social adaptation, and increases mortality. The occurrence of comorbidity reaches 69% in 18–44-year-olds, 93% in 45–64-year-olds, and 98% in those over 65 years old. In many cases, chronic heart failure (CHF) and chronic kidney disease (CKD) comorbidity has a negative impact on the quality and length of life of patients. These conditions are more and more often accompanied by diabetes mellitus (DM) or the development of serious complications on its basis.

The purpose of the study is to compare some laboratory and functional indicators in patients with chronic heart failure with diabetes and those without it.

Source and methods of research In the scientific study, 80 patients with chronic heart failure comorbidity with diabetes mellitus and without it, and developed chronic kidney disease S2 and S3a were observed. They, in turn, were

divided into two groups of 40 patients. A-group was formed by patients with SYUE+diabetes and B-group by patients without SYUE+diabetes. 45 of them (56.25%) were men and 35 (43.75%) were women. In order to solve the tasks, the scientific research work was carried out as follows. The diagnosis of SYuE and its functional classes in the patients included in the study were determined according to the criteria of the New York Heart Association (New York Heart Association, 1964) based on their complaints, anamnesis, objective examination and laboratory-instrumental examinations.

Research results. From this point of view, we conducted a comparative analysis of indicators such as laboratory, cardiac remodeling, and KFT in the group of patients with and without QD with SYuE in our observation. In this case, the left ventricular end-systolic size was 45.3 ± 1.8 mm and 50.35 ± 1.6 mm in II and III FS of SYuE in group A patients, and 42.6 ± 1.2 mm and $46.9 \pm$ in group B. was 1.5 mm, and when they were compared, no reliable differences were found ($R > 0.05$). The diastolic size of the left ventricle was 64.4 ± 1.6 mm and 59.9 ± 1.2 mm in patients with II FS of SYUE in groups A and B, and 69.35 ± 1.5 mm and $65.3 \pm$ in both groups in patients with III FS of SYUE. was equal to 1.2mm and a reliable difference was recorded ($R < 0.05$). Left ventricular end-diastolic volume was 178.3 ± 7.7 ml and 203.9 ± 7.9 ml in the II and III FS of SYuE in the first group of patients, and 174.6 ± 4.1 ml and 192.3 ± 6.8 ml in the second group. ml, no reliable differences were observed ($R > 0.05$). Left ventricular end systolic volume was 97.3 ± 5.2 ml and 83.15 ± 3.4 ml in group A and B patients with II FS of SYUE, and a reliable difference was noted ($R < 0.05$). In patients with III FS of SYUE, no reliable difference was observed between the indicators of both groups (112.3 ± 9.1 ml and 104.15 ± 8.1 ml, respectively, $R > 0.05$).

Left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) was $42.1 \pm 1.2\%$ in II FS patients with QD and $46.2 \pm 1.0\%$ in II FS patients without QD, and a reliable difference was found ($R < 0.05$). In patients with III FS of SYUE, it was $36.5 \pm 0.9\%$ and $41.7 \pm 1.3\%$ in both groups, respectively, and a highly reliable difference was noted ($R < 0.01$).

The weight of left ventricular myocardium was 233.5 ± 4.4 g and 247.5 ± 6.2 g in II and III FS of SYUE in group A patients, and 220.3 ± 3.9 g and 240.9 ± 5.5 g in group B and when they were compared, a reliable difference was found in patients with II FS ($R < 0.05$).

Summary. The analyzes conducted showed that when SYUE is comorbid, including with QD, there are negative changes in intracardiac hemodynamic indicators in accordance with its FS compared to those without QD. These were evident in left ventricular end-diastolic size, end-systolic volume, myocardial weight and ejection fraction. SYUE II-III FS patients with QD have significantly higher levels of cystatin-S, IL-6, TGF- β 1 in their blood and urine albuminuria compared to patients without QD. Also, the low level of CFT determined by cystatin-S in patients with QD indicates that this group of patients has irreversible pathological changes in the kidneys, and as a result, they develop early SBK. A comparative analysis in patients showed that exercise tolerance, quality of life, and clinical status were reliably adversely affected when SYUE was administered with QD compared to those without QD.

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